

- Yonidagi qorabayir buni sezdi shekilli, bir necha odim o‘tib, qadamini sekinlashtirdi. (M. Ismoiliy, „Farg‘ona tong otguncha“).
- Shu vaqt boloxona narvo-nida gurs-gurs qadam tovushi eshitildi. (H. G‘ulom, „Mash‘al“).
- -Mardonqul aka, – dedi u boshliqning yurishiga qadamini moslab. (A.Muxtor, „Bo‘ronlarda bordek halovat“).
- Saodatxon bir-ikki qadam bosib, yana orqasiga qaytdi. (S. Zunnunova, „Yangi direktor“).

From the presented list of words step, stride, race, remove, representing the step in English, only the word “race” has a semi-official measuring status. According to the dictionary entry, “race” [5] is defined as: “a step, a space traversed by one step - used as an indefinite unit of measure”. This is a word of Latin origin, borrowed through French. In the vast majority of cases, people who speak English, apparently, do not correlate this word with a mathematical expression for its length, but use it in everyday life as a measure that represents a step in its everyday, everyday sense. For example:

- Standing not more than twenty paces from where I was, and ten from Good, were the group of men (Haggard. King Solomon's mines, 83).
- Yvette turned away again, lingering, strolling by the full river a few paces, unwilling to go in (Lawrence. The Virgin and the Gipsy, 118).
- Wash was over there, less than ten paces off (Barnes. Battlecry, 96).
- One of the women, arriving a few paces behind the others <...>, peered into the shelter at me and Katz (Bryson. A Walk in the Woods, 206).

In the following example, the phrase “a careful two paces” is a metonymic paraphrase, indicating a distance of two geometric paces that is covered very carefully: I took a careful two paces that brought me inside the room (Brown. No Tears Through the Window, 124).

The word “step”, on the other hand, can carry an adjective. Adjectives like long, small, short simply specify the step length, for example:

- She turned the knob and took a long step in as if to avoid something nasty on the threshold (Hudson. The Tenant, 45).
- He put on his right hand as he approached her, then frowned, as she took a small step backwards (King. Needful Things, 46).
- "One small step for man..." Bernie begins, and Newill and Levin laughed (Steele. Coyote, 174). She recognized Gideon on sight, took a short step to him and then hesitated (Marric. Gideon's Week, 29).

- Assalomu alaykum, – dedim ostonadan bir qadam narida turib. (E. Raimov, „Ajab qishloq“).

- Sodiq aminning kapasi ungurdan yuz qadamcha g‘arbda, tog‘ning soyabon bo‘lib osiliv tushgan kattakon toshi ostida edi. (M. Ismoiliy, „Farg‘ona tong otguncha“).

In addition, the slight length of travel can be emphasized by cutting the stride length as a measure of distance by half, for example:

- Didn't take half a step backward before realizing it was reflection of his own face he was seeing (King. *Needful Things*, 239).

- She carried this bag slung over her shoulder, and it made her sway from side to side on the pavement, so that she would move a half-step towards me, a half-step away (Mantel. *An Experiment in Love*, 60).

In most cases, the adjectives that define the word 'step' are metonymic epithets that describe the manner in which people move. At the same time, the measuring character of the word “step” is preserved. Modern English dictionaries point to the Germanic origin of the word “step”. It is defined by the dictionary entry as: “an advance or movement of the foot made by raising the foot over a space to a different position, a space passed over by the movements of one foot beyond the other in walking” [3]. The word “step” is the most common on pages of fiction and almost always has a measuring function, for example:

- The caravan was too small for more than a few steps to be taken (Rendell. *The Crocodile Bird*, 20).

- A slender bar of starlight slid, unnoticed, up Nat's side. But it was just one step too far from Samson for an attack (Barnes. *Battlecry*, 99).

- Mary Jane slid off the coach and, on her knees, took three steps over to Eloise and began to stroke her forehead (Salinger. *Uncle Wiggity in Connecticut*, 97).

However, using the word “step” you can also express a very small distance – “a short distance, little way”: He is one step from Fargo, North Dakota, already (Burke. *Cimarron Rose*, 243). Often this word acquires a figurative meaning fixed by dictionaries: “an action” (measure, proceeding) [4], but this fact does not reduce its measuring load.

Sometimes the word “step” seem to clarify and concretize the traditional measures of distance. In the following examples, the number of steps is very important to the story, as the steps form the basis of the walks in question:

- We hiked 500 miles, a million and a quarter steps, since sailing off from Amicalola (Bryson. *A Walk in the Wood*, 212).

- Wed: As if a little thousand meters - only six hundred pairs of steps. A little, but noticeable (Gorodetsky.Knyazev Academy, 15).

In the name of the two-step dance, the word “step” continues to have a measuring function, as it indicates the number of steps in the dance movement that forms the basis of the dance. Sometimes not only the steps of a person, but also of the animal on which the journey is made, can form the basis of a measurement, but, as in the following example, not distance, but rather time. In this case, we can talk about the phenomenon of "chronotope". For example: A flying fragment stung my cheek. Within two mule strides, before I had time to react, it happened again [6] .

It should be noted that this measure is represented in English by a large number of words compared to Uzbek - step, stride, race, remove. The first three of these lexical units, like the Uzbek word step, in addition to their original meaning “step, foot movement when walking”, “distance from foot to foot during such a movement”, can mean 1) tread and 2) action or deed. The English word stride is most often used in a figurative sense. Unlike the Uzbek language, the word step represents the steps of a ladder. Since there is only one lexical unit in Uzbek to express this meaning, all changes in stride length are recorded using definitions or suffixes, for example, qadam and odim.

In conclusion, measuring words representing a step cannot be considered a frequent occurrence in the pages of English literature, since in such cases the priority is to use traditional measures: yards and feet, apparently due to the fact that they are commensurate with a person.

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INGLIZ TILIDA SO`ZLARNING KONVERSIYA USULDA YASALISHI

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada Til o`rganishdagi natija faqat muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun motivatsiya keltirishi mumkinligi, So`z yasalishi tilda mavjud bo`lgan imkoniyat va materiallar asosida yangi leksik birliklarni hosil qilish haqida, Ingliz tilida so`z tuzish o`z xususiyatlari bor. Odatda affiksatsiya - so`z qo`shimchasi yoki prefiks ildiziga qo`shib - til o`rganish qiyinchiliklarga sabab bo`lishi haqida so`z boradi.

Kalit so`zlar

til, chet tillari, motivatsiya, muvaffaqiyatga erishish, so`z yasash, o`rganish, birliklarni hosil qilish, uslub.

O'tgan asrning 60-yillari boshlarida chet tillarini o'qitish metodikasida metodikani o'qitish uslublari to'plami sifatida belgilashga urinishlar qilingan. Til materiallari bilan tanishish usullari, o'qitish usullari va shunga o'xshash narsalar paydo bo'ldi. Shu munosabat bilan ushbu atamani tushunishda ikkilik mavjud edi. Uslubiy yo'nalishlarni ko'rib chiqishdan oldin "metod" atamasi bilan bog'liq ba'zi aniqliklar kiritilishi kerak. Mahalliy uslubiy adabiyotlarda ushbu atama ikki ma'noga ega: metod uslubiy yo'nalish sifatida uslub va metod sifatida uslub - o'qitish uslublari to'plami. Ushbu atama ma'nosining ikkilikliligi quyidagi holatlar bilan bog'liq. Dastlab, ushbu atamaning birinchi ma'nosi uslubiy adabiyotlardan kelib chiqdi: tabiiy usul, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri usul va hk. Ushbu atama maxsus o'qitish tamoyillari to'plami, ya'ni asosiy ko'rsatmalar bilan tavsiflangan maxsus o'quv tizimini anglatardi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, ushbu ma'noda usul printsiplar kompleksi bilan ajralib turadi, chunki turli uslubiy tizimlarda individual printsiplar bir-biriga to'g'ri kelishi mumkin.

Uslubiy yo'nalishlarni ko'rib chiqish ikki asr davomida mavjud bo'lgan va yigirmanchi asrning boshidan beri qo'llanilmagan eng qadimgi uslub - grammatik-tarjimadan boshlanadi. Ushbu tendentsiya vakillari o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida chet tilini o'rganish nafaqat grammatikani tizimli o'rganish natijasida erishilgan aqlning gimnastikasi va mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan umumiy ma'rifiy ahamiyatga ega, deb hisoblashdi. Grammatikani o'rganish asosida